

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND FAMILY WELFARE

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Abstract: Nowadays, the position of female in the public zone as properly as in assisting the welfare of the family is gaining plenty more attention. The objective of this find out about is to decide the function of ladies in the public sector and its have an impact on on the welfare of the family. Perceptions and views of the women's husband and son on the role of ladies in the public area have been accrued as the main supply of data collection.

Key words: Roles, Women, Public, quarter, Welfare, Families

РОЛЬ ЖЕНЩИН В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ И БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИИ СЕМЬИ

Аннотация: В настоящее время все больше внимания уделяется положению женщины как в общественной сфере, так и в содействии благополучию семьи. Целью этого исследования является определение роли женщин в государственном секторе и ее влияния на благосостояние семьи. Восприятия и взгляды мужа и сына женщины на роль женщины в общественной жизни были основным источником сбора данных.

Ключевые слова: Роли, Женщины, Общественность, квартал, Благосостояние, Семьи.

OLIV TA'LIM VA OILA FAROVONLIGIDA AYOLLARNING O'RNI

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda xotin-qizlarning ham jamoat ishlarida, ham oila farovonligini oshirishdagi mavqeiga tobora ko'proq e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi ayollarning davlat sektoridagi o'rni va uning oila farovonligiga ta'sirini aniqlashdan iborat. Ayolning turmush o'rtog'i va o'g'lining jamiyat hayotidagi ayollarning egallagan o'rni haqidagi tasavvurlari va qarashlari ma'lumotlar to'plashda asosiy manba bo'ldi.

Kalit so'zlar: rollar, ayollar, jamoa, mahalla, farovonlik, oila.

I. INTRODUCTION

In general, the position of female in a number of improvement sectors in most countries, along with Indonesia is properly progressing compared to previous decades. Although there is nevertheless some discrimination in opposition to ladies in the public region, where women's role is constrained to the public zone because of lack of experience and understanding. This is one manifestation of the country wide improvement goals of most international locations aiming at human aid development, including women. With the dynamics of world adjustments that is occurring, the average circumstance of the Indonesian female is additionally experiencing some changes.

The financial crisis following several natural failures that hit Indonesia due to the fact that mid-1997 and the hovering prices of a number of kinds of items turned out to have raised a variety of serious implications in the lives of the human beings who are still dealing with the have an impact on today. The implications are pretty serious where the slow economic things to do of the humans created a low buying power. This inspired the women to actively participate in the financial and social improvement sectors in order to assist attain the needs of household lifestyles and improve the welfare of their families. The first-class of women's employment has been

increased as mirrored in the upward push of the number of female with high paying jobs as compared to the low-paying jobs in the agriculture region.

The function of female in improvement cannot be underestimated. It can be considered that in addition to an lively collaborating position in walking authorities programs, it also play an essential function in improving the welfare of the family. This in flip led to pleasant of the present day young ladies technology to continue the development of the nation's future. The participation of girls in various sectors is growing due to the fact they are diligent, conscientious, hard working, patient, honest and tough. The women's feel of responsibility, will power, enthusiasm and discipline are very high to the extent that the nearby financial improvement of Sulawesi is getting lots higher from day to day.

II.LITERATURE REVIEW.

The woman claimed to be more proactive in public roles both as perpetrators of the economic, social, cultural or political. The role of the ladies in the country's public region social transformation is getting extra substantial with minimal gender inequalities. Women now started to seem to be for work outside their residences barring carrying obligations in taking care of their homes and supporting the family's properly being. Men and girls must complement each other and gain from each other, no longer only in the family but also in the society. The increasing function of public sector female is a social phenomenon that indicates the dynamics of girls to empower potential, but on the different hand takes the outpouring of time, power and attention to the roles in their families. The learn about was limited to the learn about of the impact of the role of girls (housewives) who work in the public sector as civil servants, traders and private personnel against the welfare of the family. Public position of female (housewives) that frequently dominate home roles (roles in the family) is every so often seemed upon as having conflicting role. Thus, it is interesting to learn about the have an impact on of the position of women working in the public area (economic and social) affects the welfare of the family. It is important to be aware too if working women in the public area (economic and social) have a tremendous relationship to the welfare of the family?

The learn about was a descriptive survey comprising each quantitative and qualitative information that seeks to provide an explanation for the position of girls as agents in the public sector and its impact on the household life. This research used to be conducted in Khorezm neighborhoods via selecting three districts specifically Khonka, Khazarasp and Koshkopir. These three districts were purposely chosen as they had been primarily represented through ladies population (civil servants, business entrepreneurs and executives) both working in the public and non-public sectors. However, the sample population in this find out about was all married female with kids working in the public quarter (civil servants). A easy random sampling was achieved by taking ninety female as respondents in each district with a complete of 30 samples from 10 one-of-a-kind public sectors working women.

III.Research Methodology.Both important and secondary information had been gathered in this study. Primary information used to be received from respondents and informants thru non-public observations and interviews. Meanwhile, the secondary facts was bought from accessible archives and reports in government businesses related to women's a couple of roles and their influence on household welfare. Questionnaires and interviews were used to gather statistics about the roles of girls working in the public zone and its have an effect on on the welfare family. During the interviews, husbands and teenagers have been also current as key informants. Despite the working other halves (63 women, 70%) have efficiently carried out their dual roles in managing

the family and as public sector workers, solely 8% of the respondents still unable to commit themselves in carrying the two duties due to some in-house issues with the husband or having difficulties in managing time. Perhaps, the government or personal corporations allotted some flexi job schedules for this team of working spouse so as they each benefited their workplace job as nicely as taking care of their households at home.

IV. Analysis and results.

Nearly 27.78% of the girls have been having resistance from their husbands to work both in the public or personal sectors. The husbands felt that it is their duty and duty to go to work and earn a dwelling to guide the household despite the wives can also guide the family too through working. A whole of forty three respondents (47.78%) experienced difficulties in managing time whilst 22 respondents (24.44%) believed that it is a hassle if they work as properly as doing housework. However, majority of the respondents (54, 60%) nevertheless stay active in their social team or voluntary work. This team of female still manages to find time to socialize with their nearby at some stage in their amusement instances and this undertaking did not intrude with their core commercial enterprise as a working wife. Only very few working girl (8, 8.89%) never participate in the social community crew due to the restrained time at home when they received again from work.

Generally, it can be argued that the role of female working in the public quarter can also play more than one roles in both financial and social activities. Some of the respondents maintain very high positions in the public zone and thus managed to financially make a contribution to the household welfare and well-being. There was a significant relationship between the respondents as the primary income earner (independent variable) with an extend in the first-class of household welfare (the established variable). This relationship is evident from the contribution in meeting the desires of families, mainly in financing youth school education, protection and fitness and in assembly their day by day needs.

It can be indicated that there is a considerable relationship between income and assembly family wants the place the higher the income, the extra women can make contributions to assist meet the desires of their families. It has been stated that majority of the ladies is in a position to face the challenges in their profession course as nicely as assisting their household household income.

The results of the study confirmed that respondents are increasingly energetic in community activities and that is anticipated to have an influence on improving the great of the family.

III.CONCLUSION It can be concluded that ladies play a tremendous role in the economic and social improvement of a neighborhood in particular in the monetary help for the household well-being. There is a big relationship between the activity and participation of female in the social financial and welfare activities in the households. It is counseled that future work should be emphasized on how ladies have to play their role in the personal area transformation towards higher productiveness and economic boom of the country.

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